

Gezi - 10 Years After, Maxim Gorki Theatre, 26 May - 25 June, 2023

Gezinema World Cinema Documentaries

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Co-curated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

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Screening: The Monopoly of Violence, 2020

As anger and resentment grow in the face of social inequalities, many citizens-led protests are being repressed with an ever-increasing violence. In MONOPOLY OF VIOLENCE, David Dufresne gathers a panel of citizens to question, exchange and confront their views on the social order and the legitimacy of the use of force by the State.

Q&A Session with Gamze Elvan, moderated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy, translated by Erden Kosova

Gamze Elvan was born in Istanbul-Beyoğlu. She graduated from Yeditepe University, Department of Turkish Language and Literature. She has been working as an editor and reporter for the independent digital news portal Medyascope since 2015. She was the editor of the main news broadcast program Güne Bakış for a while, as well as the editor of News Weekend and Gökkuşluğu Bulletin. Every morning, she hosts Medyascope's podcast Güne Başlarken where she reports on current events. She is interested in current politics and social developments.

ŞE: Hi everyone, thank you for staying. Today we are doing something a little different for the Q & A session. We have invited Gamze Elvan and we are very happy she was able to make it. I met Gamze personally in 2019 when I also started working at Medyascope. As I said, Medyascope is one of the most important independent digital media outlets in Turkey. Gamze is still there, she still works for Medyascope. She is an editor of the evening broadcast as well as the Gökkuşluğu Bülteni, which is a special news report on LGBTQI+ developments in Turkey, and she also runs the morning podcast show that gives updates on current events. Although I met Gamze 2 years ago, as the Turkish public, we all got to know her in 2013 when she was only 17 years old. In June 2013, her brother Berkin Elvan was hit by a teargas canister in the Okmeydanı district of Istanbul during the Gezi Park protests. Berkin fell into a coma and remained in a coma for 269 days after which he succumbed to his fatal injuries and passed away. Gamze's family has been fighting in a country where justice is barely ever served to put Berkin's murderer in prison and there are also several other court cases, which she will share with us because 10 years is a very long time. Erdoğan, current president, prime minister back in the day, said that he himself gave the order to shoot. So he has accepted that he himself is the murderer of Berkin.

Gamze, thank you so much for being here. Can you please give us a little rundown of you and your family's fight for justice in the last 10 years? What have you been facing, what is the current situation of the case? I know there is currently also a case against your parents for insulting the president and they are also facing jail time. Do you mind giving us a short rundown of your fight for justice?

GE: First of all, thank you for the invitation. Before starting I would like to commemorate all the people that lost their lives during the Gezi Park protests. At the same time, my greetings to all the people who are imprisoned in the Gezi trial. When Berkin, my brother, was shot he was 14 and I was 17. When Berkin died I was 18 and at that time, I had no idea what a fight for justice meant. Of course I knew that people were fighting for their rights and for justice in the neighbourhood I was living in, Okmeydanı, a traditional neighbourhood for revolutionaries. But I never had to claim justice before I lost my brother. After my brother was hospitalised, that is after the tear gas canister hit his head on June 16, 2013, we met a lot of lawyers, and the judicial process started. Yet the murderer of Berkin only came to light 3 years later. We did not know anything about the perpetrator until then. The trial for the perpetrator was between 2016 and 2021, and we had to wait 9 years until a verdict was given. There was only a single person that was put on trial and that was the perpetrator but it was never extended to the people who ordered this crime. The murderer received a 16-year sentence but the Higher Court still has not executed this sentence as this is still suspended. When Berkin died he was 16 kilos, so it's as though each year equates to each kilo. Berkin's murderer is still in service in Eastern Turkey. Whether he is still killing a child at the moment, I don't know, I'm worried. The European Court of Human Rights has demanded the interrogation of the Istanbul Police Department and the Governor of Istanbul, who are responsible for the shooting or the order of the shooting of Berkin, but Turkey has still not implemented this decision. And finally, there is President Erdoğan, who was the Prime Minister when Berkin was shot and killed. We say he is Berkin's murderer because in the public space, he said he gave the order of the shooting and in this same space he made his supporters to boo my mother. Now my mother and my father are being trialled for calling him a murderer. In September there is a possibility they might be sentenced to prison but Berkin's murderer is still out on the loose. Finally one of our lawyers, Can Atalay, was also put on trial in relation to the Gezi protests and his search for justice also ended in Silivri prison¹.

ŞE: Thank you Erden, thank you Gamze. I know it is not easy to go through this, so please feel free to stop me whenever you want.

I would like to ask you about your experiences as a journalist but before that, I mean this murder happened when you were only 17 years old, and immediately after that you began this fight for justice. You became involved with lawyers and larger communities that wanted to show support. As a first question: how has your perception of police violence and justice changed after Berkin got shot, because you mentioned that you also came from Okmeydanı, and obviously Okmeydanı is - for those of you who are not familiar with Istanbul - let's say it's home to revolutionary ideas and groups, so it's a politically very engaged neighbourhood as well. I would assume that when you were younger, you were already exposed to both police violence, aware at least of police surveillance, which was always very tight in your neighbourhood and aware of

¹ Silivri Prison has been known for the detention of individuals involved in political activism, including journalists, human rights defenders, opposition figures, and members of various political and social movements.

these interactions. Can you talk about that part of your life and when that happened to you, what happened to Berkin, how that changed your perception?

GE: As you said, I was already familiar with police violence due to the neighbourhood I was living in. However, when the Gezi protests began, as we just saw in the film earlier, I was able to see that quite a few people lost their eyes, or other organs getting mutilated or being hit on their heads with gas canisters when following the news. I was aware of what was happening and it was always worrying for me. I also took part in the Gezi protests and something could have happened to me too, of course, but I didn't know how this process was going to affect me but I could see what was happening. For instance, 2 days before Berkin died, we had commemorated the loss of Ethem Sarisülük, another young person who was killed due to police violence in Ankara.² During this ceremony, my brother Berkin had read a poem, and 2 days later we found ourselves in the same type of environment of worry, sadness and anger. Therefore, my Gezi experience of police violence was no longer only related to worry for me, this turned into anger and my desire to hold people accountable and bring things to justice has grown. I was 17 when Berkin died, now I am 27 and in the last 10 years of my fight for justice, I always wanted to promote the rights of the people who were subjected to police violence and legal aggressions.

ŞE: Speaking of the support, in David Dufrasne's film which focuses on the Gilets Jaunes Movement in France, we also saw that there were a lot of young children and particularly boys coming from the banlieu, children of colour, who were also victims of police violence - at least in reference to the film - since the 1980s. Can you speak a little about these support networks that your family was part of? Who was there for you, whether it's civil society, or maybe more international networks, and how has this support sustained itself over the last 10 years?

GE: After 16th of June, the day Berkin was shot, I began to get to know people I was unfamiliar with. As a family we always felt that all the people who were present at Gezi were beside us. All the opposition circles, the leftists, the revolutionaries were always by our side. Therefore, 9 months after, when Berkin lost his life, crowds of people attended Berkin's funerary ceremony, and this spirit of togetherness had really helped me. I would also like to add, when Berkin was shot, I believe the government indicated their guilt as the president at the time, Abdullah Gül, the nationalists, the ministers, as in: Erdoğan's ministers, all sent us their condolences but a couple of days later, they started with their accusations. The people that gave me the most strength were the families of the victims who lost their lives during the Gezi Park protests and

² Ethem Sarisülük was shot in the head by the police officer Ahmet Şahbaz. He was in a coma for 12 days and declared brain dead on June 12, 2013.

the “Cumartesi Anneleri” (Saturday Mothers)³ who for 28 years have demonstrated their fight for justice over the disappearance of their children in custody.

ŞE: Gamze, maybe we can speak about your experience as a journalist. You’ve been working for Medyascope since 2015. So that’s 8 years ago. You were 19 when you started working there. How has your experience there - what have you seen or noticed since 2015 in terms of developments and freedom of expression, and police violence; you’ve been looking at the whole country, have you seen differences in the way police exists or is able to exist in the West of the country versus in other regions, because in 2015, after the elections we had a short period of civil war let’s say, that started in the East. Maybe you can give us a rundown of your experiences in the media, especially the independent media.

GE: I began working in media and am trying to continue my career in relatively independent media. However, I do observe that when working in the media, you are forcibly biased because of the power of the government’ control and management over it. It enables a situation in which you cannot remain neutral. On the other hand, when you do your work as a journalist, you can be arrested. Even if you attempt objective journalism you can end up being persecuted as is the case with so many journalists. For instance, the case of Can Dündar⁴ alone is quite telling, who now lives in exile in Germany, and forcibly fled the country because of the news he revealed in Turkey. Just like we have seen in The Monopoly of Violence, when journalists follow any protest or any news, they can be exposed to police violence, and are not allowed to take any footage of

³ Saturday Mothers are a group of women and their families, who gather every Saturday in Istanbul's Galatasaray Square to protest against the enforced disappearances of their loved ones. The group began in the 1990s as a response to the human rights violations and state-sanctioned violence committed during the conflict between the Turkish government and the Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK). The Saturday Mothers' peaceful protests have become a symbol of resilience, human rights activism, and a quest for justice in Turkey. Their persistent efforts have garnered international attention and support from human rights organisations. However, the Turkish government has often responded to these protests with police interventions, detentions, and restrictions on their gatherings, leading to further criticism of human rights violations.

⁴ In 2015, as the editor-in-chief of the newspaper Cumhuriyet, Can Dündar published a report revealing Turkish intelligence's alleged arms shipments to Syrian rebel groups. This exposé led to his arrest and subsequent trial on charges of revealing state secrets. While released on bail pending trial, Dündar decided to leave Turkey and seek refuge in Berlin. In Berlin, Dündar established the online news platform Özgürüz ("We are Free") to provide an independent platform for journalism and commentary. Dündar's exile represents a larger trend of journalists and intellectuals leaving Turkey due to concerns over the shrinking space for freedom of speech and press freedom. His case drew international attention to the erosion of media freedom and the plight of journalists in Turkey, making him a symbol of resistance and an advocate for democratic values and human rights.

this.⁵ Following the last very critical election in Turkey we did believe the media landscape could change and become more independent, but unfortunately, this change did not take place. What I now fear is that journalists may begin self-censoring.

Q: I am very sorry for what happened to your brother. We come from Hong Kong and also participated in protests where extensive police violence happened in 2019. In terms of the scale of the injuries incurred in Istanbul or France, I believe the scale there would be much greater, in terms of physical injuries. My first question is: now that you are still in your country, which gives you a lot of pain, but also I believe there is a reason why you are staying there and pursuing an independent journalist career, which is very noble - but what is your fuel to stay in the country, what drives you to continue despite the pain of doing what you are doing?

My second question is related to: people like us, immigrants who now live in Berlin, we feel like it's very difficult for us to talk to the people who are still living in Hong Kong, and the same applies to the more liberal Russians here who left that crazy regime - we feel a gap in terms of understanding the world. How do you see this bridge, from a Turkish perspective, of those people who live in exile and those who are suffering in Turkey; how can this gap be narrowed?

GE: First of all, thank you very much. What keeps me going is my brother and what I write, because if I or journalists like myself were to leave the country and stop reporting on the people who experience violations of their rights, then nobody will report this. As for your second question, with regards to immigration, I am not sure how to approach this but what I observe is that there are a large number of people, especially young people, immigrating from Turkey because they have lost hope for the future and have great worries. At the same time, people who experience injustices consider leaving Turkey and they do but to be able to close the gap that emerges, democracy needs to come to Turkey. Right now, it doesn't look like it is going to happen, and people will continue to immigrate from Turkey and I think they are quite right in doing so.

ŞE: I would like to say a few words in regard to your second question addressing the gap between the so-called diaspora and those in Turkey. My research at the Film University Babelsberg in the context of my Marie Curie postdoctoral fellowship, has been focusing on migration and its impact on audio-visual production, particularly in a context where the producer of the content is an activist. This has been labelled as a New Wave migration and different from the migration from Turkey to Germany over the last 60 years. I don't think it makes sense to separate in terms of clear-cut lines as waves of migration have various different reasons, but I believe diaspora reproduces the same dynamics in Turkey -

⁵ In Turkey, a government circular was published on 30 April 2020, banning all audio-visual recordings of citizens and police at protests, on the grounds that these recordings breached the privacy of individuals. The circular aimed to reduce police accountability to the public and prevent evidence collection, especially in cases where police committed violence against demonstrators. As for France, recording during protests is allowed as long as it does not interfere with the functioning of public order or violate other individuals' privacy rights. It is important to note that individuals have faced legal consequences for recording protests.

Berlin is a microcosm of Turkey and you see the same political groups reproduce themselves. I believe our role is to bridge that gap - that diaspora has the possibility to go beyond the politics in Turkey and create a dialogue beyond that, that emphasises their diasporic identities and create commonality along those lines.

For the past 2 weeks, we've been having a series of panels and in one of them, the notion of the Gezi spirit was raised and how we are able to do a festival about Gezi here, and this is unimaginable, obviously in Turkey and one of the guests, who is a professor at Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University in Istanbul, Begüm Özden Firat, she said the Gezi spirit still exists, we are still living Gezi in Turkey because there still is so much going on, so much to fight for. We still have to organise ourselves and fight so Gezi - we are still living it whereas here, she came to the festival, she had a look at all the events and said: you guys have a nostalgic look at Gezi, you are remembering Gezi because here there are other battles, and I'm not saying living here is easy in any kind of way, but you have a nostalgic look at Gezi.

So Gamze, for you - where do you see the Gezi spirit now, do you still feel it in your everyday life, how is this solidarity built beyond differences that existed or were established at the park prevailing today?

GE: I had to pay a very heavy price. I was able to experience the Gezi spirit for 15 days. It was not the same for me, Şirin, unfortunately. The only thing that kept me on my feet was the people's solidarity. I was able to hold on to this but in Turkey, every day someone is killed and therefore, everyone is able to forget everything very quickly, unfortunately. Finally, I want to say, if we could have managed to maintain the memory of what happened, perhaps the election results could have been different and people who are imprisoned could be free, and people would not have been killed but alive.

ŞE: Thank you all so much for coming and for staying with us. Gamze, thank you so much for being with us. Erden, thank you for the translation.

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